

Potential of Using Natural Resources of Manisa (Turkey) in Adventure Tourism

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ABSTRACT

The subject and purpose of this paper is to analyze the natural attractions of the province of Manisa, where adventure tourism in Turkey can take action immediately with small initiatives. The study was prepared by two methods: qualitative research and geographical area research. Qualitative data were used by making in-depth descriptions and interpretations with the tourism geography approach, and thematic systematic flow was provided from the theory to the findings in the content. Types, components, activities and effects in adventure tourism constitutes the theoretical framework of the study. Geographical field research was carried out in the form of field observations with the competence given by the geographer identity of the authors. The design of this qualitative research is a situation analysis. The findings related to Manisa have been shaped upon the current situation and potential of adventure tourism (Spil Mountain National Park, Kula-Salihli Geopark, Gediz River, Gölarmara Lake, hiking routes, etc.). The study has gained originality with the suggestions developed within the scope of the components, activities, appropriate areas, and research projects by synthesizing the subjects in theoretical framework with Manisa. The contribution of the study to the research region, literature and tourism geography is to reveal that adventure tourism can be more successful if it is integrated with other tourism types that intersect with it on the basis of space and activities than being implemented by itself. Indeed, the adventure tourism in Manisa has the capacity to integrate with geotourism, mountain tourism, sports tourism and exploration tourism.

1. Introduction

The international tourism industry is increasingly segmented with the growth of different niches. Adventure tourism is one of the rapidly developing niche sectors, and due to its multiplier effects, its economic footprint has expanded a lot. It is not easy to define adventure tourism and draw its boundaries. For example, some scientists consider adventure tourism to be part of cultural tourism and ecotourism. Although there is no universal definition of adventure tourism, it is “everything based on adventure” from the point of view of tourists. In terms of supply, it is the marketing of a wide range of activities within the scope of adventure tourism. As well as activities in adventure tourism, transportation and accommodation are considered an adventure in themselves.

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This study focuses on adventure tourism in Manisa. The aim is to determine the suitability (potential) of natural resources for adventure tourism, to re-evaluate and to develop recommendations about the future. The original side of this work is that it is the first publication that deals with adventure tourism in Manisa under this name, as well as a thematic and spatial integration approach. The study is designed in two main parts: the theoretical framework and adventure tourism in Manisa (findings). In this context, the types, components and activities included in the theoretical content were compared with the Manisa data in the findings and the necessary interpretations (synthesis) were made.

The main reason for this study, which is prepared with the tourism geography approach, is twofold. First, the reasons that are caused outside of Manisa: the rising trend of adventure tourism, the fact that it has not yet reached the level of a sector or industry in Turkey although it can integrate with other types of tourism with its many activities, and the consequential gap in the Turkish literature. Second, the reasons related to Manisa: the partial evaluation of the tourism potential of Manisa on the basis of cultural tourism, faith tourism, thermal tourism, ecotourism and rural tourism, and the fact that the province cannot show a certain breakthrough in tourism. These findings have led us to the conclusion that adventure tourism may contribute to Manisa tourism. The content of the study shows a flow from the general (theoretical) to the specific (research field), and the general and the specific are brought together by analysis and synthesis. The geographer identity of the authors has made it necessary to consider adventure tourism on the basis of tourism geography. Some of the topics of potential detection, use of potential, distribution, comparison, demand, services and effects in tourism geography have been moved to this study. In the design of the research, the following topics are included: first, adventure tourism is outlined (development and competitiveness, types and components, activities, and other tourism types vertices, effects, trends, and future); second, the findings are presented (Manisa, an overview of the current state of tourism and adventure tourism, the potential for the development of adventure tourism in Manisa and re-evaluation, SWOT analysis). The study ends with discussion, conclusions and suggestions.

2. Literature Review

It is observed that adventure tourism publications have started to multiply since the 1980s. While literature review is included as a section in publications (Taylor & Carra, 2021; Mykletun, 2018; Buckley, 2010), there are also works that are entirely literature research. The most comprehensive systematic study of adventure tourism literature was conducted by Rantala et al. (2016b). Between 1981 and 2014, the authors compiled the resources related to adventure tourism with a certain method, obtained 1257 references and divided them into 11 categories. By categories, the number of works are as follows: tourism (641), outdoor recreation (232), outdoor/adventure education (100), leisure (66), discovery (51), travel and medical illness (44), space tourism (37), adventure therapy (28), the environment (21), sex

tourism (18) and mobility (15). The distribution of works by year began to increase after the 2000s. With the increasing interest in adventure tourism activities, the number of publications and the variety of topics will increase even more in the coming years. Although there is no publication focused directly on adventure tourism in Manisa, there are various studies on nature tourism and ecotourism. The Spil Mountain National Park is the most researched region (Taşlıgil, 1994; Semenderoğlu et al., 2005; Yasak & Durukan, 2017). In a large number of plans, adventure tourism has been mentioned indirectly, in a limited form and under different names (TKDK, 2015; T.C. Zafer Kalkınma Ajansı, 2016a, 2016b; Şehzadeler Kaymakamlığı, 2017).

3. Methodology

The main purpose of this study is to determine the suitability of natural resources in Manisa for adventure tourism. The secondary goal is a structure that complements each other: to reveal how natural resources can be re-evaluated in Manisa, and to question the future of adventure tourism in Manisa by taking into account global trends. These hypotheses are developed in the study: (1) there are many potential natural resources for the adventure tourism in Manisa; (2) natural resources in Manisa should be re-evaluated regarding the adventure tourism with new approaches; (3) there are many obstacles to the development of adventure tourism in Manisa on its own; (4) so that adventure tourism can have a future in Manisa, it must be integrated with many types of tourism. Since the study is a qualitative research, qualitative data were used. The data collection tools are scientific resources, corporate researches, plans, reports as well as some official websites. Mostly up-to-date sources were selected from the literature and the literature in Turkish was used for Manisa. Foreign literature was given importance in the theoretical part of the study which is a case study (adventure tourism) and at the same time a current situation study. In this context, the subject has been examined in depth and holistically in all aspects. Key concepts are included before the findings. The concepts are handled in an order from the center of adventure tourism outward. The findings were presented together with descriptive compilation and field observations, and were synthesized by establishing the relation with the concepts. Analytical generalizations were reached in the conclusion.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. The outlines of adventure tourism

Adventure tourism has entered the process of growth worldwide, with the proliferation of new destinations catering to travelers seeking unique experiences. While adventure tourists push their own cultural, physical and geographical comfort limits, extreme adventurers choose hard-to-reach places and know no limits in activities. Adventure tourism has common features with sustainable tourism, conservation tourism, responsible tourism, pro-poor tourism, community-based tourism, voluntary tourism, ecotourism and geotourism. The success of the sector

depends primarily on the government policies, as well as the innovative and compelling products developed by the sector (UNWTO, 2014: 9-10, 12, 14, 24). Adventure tourism includes activities with relative risk, mostly performed in natural environments, requiring physical effort and certain skills. Beyond the natural dimension of adventure tourism, visiting cultural heritage sites and communicating with the host society can be the main motivation source (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 6, 24). A holistic approach to adventure tourism is very important. Success in adventure tourism depends on a coordinated effort between industry, government, local communities and projects (ATTA, 2018: 38). Swarbrooke et al. (2003: 135) schematized the structural elements of the sector as follows (Fig. 1):

Fig. 1. The structure of the adventure tourism industry
Source: Swarbrooke et al. (2003)

4.1.1. Development and competitiveness

These institutions have a big role in making adventure tourism one of the fastest growing niches in the global tourism economy. Although developed countries dominate adventure tourism today, there are many opportunities for the development of this type of tourism in many parts of the world (McKay, 2013: 52). Adventure tourism is called “turning back in the time tunnel”. For example, in North America, travelers want to return to the colonization period (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 4). Swarbrooke et al. (2003: 38) present examples from the UK that old themes in adventure tourism are preserved even today: exploration and adventure, student exchange, ecotourism, artificial environments, hunting, pilgrims, missionary, travel writing, natural historians, women travellers and so on. According to the Adventure Tourism Development Index (ATDI) jointly prepared by George Washington

University (GW) and Adventure Travel Trade Association (ATTA), the top 10 countries with the highest competitive power and developing countries are as follows (ATTA & GW, 2020: 5) (Table 1).

Table 1. Top ten ranked countries in 2020

Rank*	Developed countries rankings	Developing countries rankings
1	Iceland	Czech Republic
2	Switzerland	Chile
3	New Zealand	Slovak Republic
4	Germany	Slovenia
5	Norway	Israel
6	Finland	Estonia
7	Sweden	Poland
8	Canada	Bulgaria
9	Denmark	Romania
10	Australia	Costa Rica

Source: ATTA and GW (2020)

*Recall that the ATDI does not capture visitor numbers and is not a ranking for volume of tourists.

At the same time with the index, the strengths and weaknesses of destinations in adventure tourism are determined, and competitive advantages in the market are measured in three categories (Table 2):

Table 2. The ATDI examines ten factors (10 pillars of adventure market competitiveness) in three categories

Safe and welcoming	Adventure	Readiness
1. Sustainable development	5. Adventure resources	7. Humanitarian
2. Safety	6. Entrepreneurship	8. Infrastructure
3. Natural resources		9. Cultural resources
4. Health		10. Image

Source: ATTA and GW (2020)

As a result, it is argued that competitiveness in adventure tourism is based on a network of interconnected factors, therefore tourism governance among its institutions is essential (ATTA, 2020: 5).

4.1.2. Types and components

There are two main types of adventure tourism: (1) *soft*: slow, easy, light, (2) *hard*: hard, power, heavy, extreme. Recent studies show that soft ones are becoming more in demand in adventures (Rantala, 2018a: 3-4). The easiest way to define an adventure trip as soft or hard is to base it on its primary (main) purpose (UNWTO, 2014: 10, 12). *Soft/easy adventure tourism* is mostly carried out with experienced guides (Rantala, 2018a: 3-4, 21-22). The products of this segment are intended for a wide audience, therefore, soft activities occupy the highest share in the tourism sector. Hard/difficult adventure tourism is preferred for challenging activities because it

involves self-transcendence, risk and adrenaline, such as rock and ice climbing, skydiving, rafting and scuba diving. Such products appeal to a specific target audience, require technical skills and special equipment, the desire to travel to unique places stands out. Another classification in adventure tourism is based on the environment in which activities are carried out, and those that are carried out on land are in greater demand in the tourism sector (KPMG International, 2010: 20-21; Kumar & Deshmukh, 2021: 53). Nowadays, adventure tourism is no longer the focus of attention only for adventurers, and well-controlled outdoor activities with family participation have become widespread (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 6-7).

Prominent components in adventure tourism:

Products, product preparers marketing: A large number of products are created according to the tourist profile and two basic types (soft and hard) in adventure tourism. These are activities such as transportation, accommodation, eating and drinking, shopping, etc. The fact that there are a lot of unforeseen risks in adventure tourism requires the existence of alternative products at all times. The success of manufacturers in product and market diversity makes marketing possible throughout the year. Product creators, tourists and locals are considered to be the most critical components of adventure tourism. Those who work in adventure tourism in Québec are advised to be passionate about nature, to perceive nature correctly, to protect the natural and cultural environment, to raise awareness of guides and customers about environmental protection, to adapt to the needs of customers (Commission Canadienne du Tourisme, 2000: 23-25, 35-36, 80). Tour operators, trade fairs, social media and websites are used in the promotion and marketing of adventure tourism. Soft species contributed the most to this market in 2020. While activities on land had the highest share in this year, there was also an increase in air-based activities (Kumar & Deshmukh, 2021: 37, 48-49).

Tourists, travelers, adventurers, guides: Schmid et al. (2013: 1) state that those who demand adventure are different from mass tourists, they want to have a real experience to get out of their routine. According to ATTA's 2018 report, recent adventure travelers have turned to mental activities, and female travelers have increased in number (ATTA, 2018: 9, 14-15, 20-22, 28-29). In another publication by ATTA (2020: 8), it is written that travelers are emotionally motivated, believe in challenge and often transformation and intend to make a positive impact on the natural environment and local communities. McKay (2013: 41-42), on the other hand, suggests that some tourists participate in adventure tourism in order to refresh their own image and achieve social status (McKay, 2013: 41-42). The expectations from the guides are that they should be friendly, communicative, enthusiastic and attentive to details, with sufficient skills. A guide should receive continuing education and strengthen his expertise. (Commission Canadienne du Tourisme, 2000: 23-25).

Destinations: Swarbrooke et al. (2003: 127) defines destination which is an important component of adventure tourism through these features: (1) they could be traditional or modern, (2) geographic location is very important, (3) they gain expertise in the specific activities, (4) seasonality is in question (5) some other types

of tourism has a variety of destinations (6) the climatic challenges, lack of infrastructure and political tensions do not reduce interest to them, (7) opportunities for adventure tourism may be at local and regional level. A tour package includes a route, a guide, activities, visits, hotels, food and drink, transportation, security (Quebec Turizm, 2002: 89). Canada, the USA, China, Nepal, Mongolia, India, Maldives, Thailand, Scotland, Switzerland, Russia, Norway, Portugal, Brazil, Costa Rica, Chile, Ecuador, Fiji, Samoa, Papua New Guinea, Australia, New Zealand, and the polar regions are among the famous destinations of adventure tourism (Swarbrooke et al., 2003: 127).

4.1.3. Activities

Adventure activities are closely related to individual causes, infrastructure, services, promotion and marketing. On the other hand, factors such as “fashion”, “habit” and “tradition” have diversified adventure products from the past to the present, new ones have been added alongside the classic ones, and this process continues with “global and modern” trends. The activities of adventure tourism are classified by ATTA in the following table by types (ATTA, 2013: 4; Table 3):

Table 3. Adventure tourism activities by type

Activity	Type	Activity	Type
Archeological expedition	Soft	Hunting	Soft
Attending local festival	Other	Kayaking/sea/whitewater	Soft
Backpacking	Soft	Learning a new language	Other
Birdwatching	Soft	Orienteering	Soft
Camping	Soft	Rafting	Soft
Canoening	Soft	Research expeditions	Soft
Caving	Hard	Safaris	Soft
Climbing (mountain/rock)	Hard	Sailing	Soft
Cruise	Other	Scuba diving	Soft
Cultural activities	Other	Snorkeling	Soft
Ecotourism	Soft	Skiing/snowboarding	Soft
Educational programs	Soft	Surfing	Soft
Env. sustainable activities	Soft	Trekking	Hard
Fishing/fly-fishing	Soft	Walking tours	Other
Getting to know the locals	Other	Visiting friends/family	Other
Hiking	Soft	Visiting historical sites	Other
Horseback riding	Soft	Volunteer tourism	Soft

Source: ATTA (2013)

Activities are also divided into 4 groups by Swarbrooke et al. (2003: 127) according to the place and venue where they are performed: on land (hiking, etc.); in the air (space travel, balloon travel, etc.); mind-oriented (pilgrimage, virtual reality, etc.) and water (rafting, diving, etc.).

4.1.4. Intersections with other types of tourism

When it comes to adventure tourism and classification of activities, it is seen that adventure tourism is closely related to many types of tourism. Nature tourism, outdoor tourism, ecotourism and exploration tourism intersect with adventure tourism and share the same products (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 5). Many more are added to these types, such as recreational tourism, camping-caravan tourism, geotourism, sport tourism (sport tourism), hiking tourism, rafting tourism, educational tourism and artificial-environment adventure tourism. In recent years, nature tourism has gained significant momentum as health awareness has increased. Its spatial boundaries have expanded greatly with the motto of “lifelong experience”, and it has been integrated with adventure tourism. Therefore, nature tourism sometimes uses a number of adventure activities (KPMG International, 2010: 18-19, 23). Another approach (Rantala et al., 2018a: 2) is that adventure tourism has turned into nature tourism (as in Finland) as a result of the “softening of adventures”. “Friluftsliv”, which is mentioned a lot in adventure tourism in foreign literature, is a philosophy of life compatible with Scandinavian traditions, partly containing adventure, focusing on exploration, learning, establishing emotional ties with space and society, belonging, sociability and freedom. In this context, Friluftsliv is defined as *spending quality time with other people, intertwined with nature through ecosystem experiences and interactions* (Mykletun, 2018: 320-321). Although the traditional friluftsliv is in the process of changing with tourists looking for luxury, comfort and excitement, the number of tourists who want to break away from modernity is not small (Westskog, 2021: 345). Indeed, 90% of the Norwegian population’s participation in outdoor life and recreational activities shows the importance given to friluftslive (Lagestad et al., (2019: 21-23). Ecotourism is the type of tourism that displays the most comprehensive integration with adventure tourism. Because ecotourism products are very similar or even the same as adventure products (KPMG International, 2010: 18-19). While ecotourism mainly emphasizes nature conservation and environmental awareness, adventure tourism is more focused on recreational opportunities. The comparisons of J. Priskin, an ecotourism expert, are interesting: if you have skied and spent the night in a cottage, you are participating in “soft adventure tourism”, whereas if you ski with a guide who teaches you about your natural environment and how to protect it, and if your stay is organized by a tour operator, it means that you have done ecotourism (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 5-6). While traditional adventure tourism requires struggle with nature, mostly outdoors, many people today are also pursuing new challenges in artificial environments and indoors. This new phenomenon called adventure tourism in artificial environment, adventure forests, theme parks, amusement parks, artificial ski slopes, artificial waves, virtual reality simulators etc. has become very popular recently. At the same time, the fact that urban artificial environment adventure programs provide personal development opportunities similar to traditional nature exploration programs shows that they will become more widespread in the future (Swarbrooke et al., 2003: 47, 107).

4.1.5. Influences, trends and the future

The economic effects of adventure tourism on a destination are mostly in the form of positive effects. Adventure tourism supports local entrepreneurs and families, creates new jobs, and benefits local governments. However, in developing countries, many problems arise from foreign enterprises to the sector. Also, costs of adventure tourism outstrip health and education expenses in local budgets, and seasonal intensity strains infrastructure (Swarbrooke et al., 2003: 193-196). Moreover, environmental impacts in adventure tourism are generally negative due to direct contact with the physical environment. In particular, the establishment of facilities for activities, the release of waste to the mountains, high-volume safari tours, interventions in wildlife, damage to coral reefs are the most striking examples (Swarbrooke et al., 2003: 193-196).

Varley and Semple (2015: 83) look at the issue of effects from the tourist's perspective as follows: to bask on rocks eroded by glacial erosion; to watch the vast landscapes merge with the sky; to cook with wild herbs; to encounter wild animals; to sleep in the open air and to watch the stars, in short, to be a part of natural life creates unique inner experiences. The social effects of adventure tourism are seen as a problem due to the fact that many adventurers from developed countries visit very different cultures. For example, in Indonesia, the open dress of backpackers creates anxiety among the local population, and tourists can be bad role models, especially for young people. Adventure tourists undoubtedly also have positive social effects such as volunteering in conservation and charity projects, educating local people and giving tourists the opportunity to renew themselves. On the other hand, backpackers going to India and other Asian countries are seen to question their lives and even change their religion (Swarbrooke et al., 2003: 193-196).

In recent years, it has been witnessed that adventure-oriented touristic destinations have increased, new products and new marketing strategies have developed. Day by day more and more methods and tools for planning adventure programs are emerging. One of the new trends is the proliferation of luxury-oriented customers. Other trends are listed as follows: to be interested in "exploration" trips, to have a "responsible" understanding of travel, "helping" a community, "to protect" wild animals and nature, to choose "short" and "soft" adventure activities, etc. (ESG-UQAM, 2012: 9-10, 17, 23, 25). ATTA (2018: 28) states that solo travels are increasing among adventure travelers, and special routes and booking platforms are formed. According to ATTA's Adventure Travel Trends 2022 research (Kelly, 2022), the ten trends that will impact adventure travel are: (1) international travel improves, (2) domestic travel stays strong, (3) travel's environmental impact awareness, (4) travel's environmental impact action, (5) sustainable food and drink, (6) the nomad economy, (7) diversity, equity, and inclusion is being recognized, (8) ruralization and communitization of travel, (9) social divides deepen, (10) the financialization of travel. The following trends are also included: wellness, transformational experience, self-guided tours, COVID-19 pandemic, booking fluctuations.

UNWTO draws attention to the following issues that will affect the future of adventure tourism destinations: climate change, responsible tourism, waste reduction, income retention, rural people's pride in their culture (UNWTO, 2014: 83). Buckley (2006: 475-477) focuses on products related to the future: henceforth, many adventure activities will turn into compound products and entail individual package tours. In the sector, e-magazines, e-mails, websites, television, movies, fashion, mobile phones, etc. will benefitted. The level of luxury services offered on adventure tours will continue to increase. Swarbrooke et al. (2003: 117, 196-197, 283-284), on the other hand, advocate these views: those who have not yet taken an adventure tourism holiday will increase international movement in the future, there will be a growth in the participation of families in adventure tourism, short adventure packages will be preferred, personal adventure travels will increase, especially climate change and political factors may threaten the growth of this sector. The same authors suggest the following research on the future of adventure tourism: emotional (spiritual) adventure tourism, urban artificial adventure tourism, intercultural differences in the perception of adventure tourism, effects, motivations and purchasing decisions, entrepreneurship and management, demographic profile, definitions, ethical dimension, role of media, data and market.

4.2. An overview of Manisa tourism and the current state of adventure tourism

Manisa is located in the Aegean Region in the west of Turkey. Manisa is also one of the 81 provinces of Turkey and has a large territory (1,232 km²) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Geographical location of Manisa in Turkey
 Source: T. R. Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure

The history of settlements in the province goes back to prehistory, but its special place in history belongs to the Ottoman Period. The deep historical past on the territory of the province has left a rich cultural heritage. The universal cultural values (ancient cities, mosques, residential architecture, etc.) as well as the rural

culture of the province (traditions, local products, villages, crafts, cuisine, etc.) are so diverse that local identities have been preserved. The geographical location of the province of Manisa and the location of the city center have made various economic activities that bring transportation facilities, and agriculture is the leading one. The natural geographical resources of Manisa are as diverse as cultural values, and they all offer a charm for tourism. These include, first of all, the Mount Spil (1513 m), the Bozdağlar Plateau, Kula volcanic areas, Gediz River, Gölarmara Lake and geothermal waters (Kurşunlu hot springs, etc.). Today, cultural tourism, faith tourism, rural tourism, ecotourism and thermal tourism in Manisa have shown a moderate and domestic-market-weighted development. The source of demand is İzmir and its surrounding provinces. Therefore, it can be said that Manisa has a regional market in tourism. Manisa's access to the national and international market is more limited and three touristic product groups provide this opportunity: Ottoman religious buildings, Kula-Salihli Geopark and the ancient city of Sardis which had been the capital of the Lydian Kingdom.

Considering the current structure of adventure tourism in Manisa, it can be said that the types of activities are limited, and that adventure tourism in itself has not yet developed, or rather it has not become an economic sector. In this case, it can be mentioned that the development of day-to-day nature-based activities is more common. Paragliding, mountain biking, ATV tours, orienteering, hiking, backpacking trips, horse riding, geopark and national park visits are among the main activities. The types and places of all these activities are shown in the table below (Table 4, Fig. 8):

Table 4. Current features of adventure tourism in Manisa

Activity name	Type	Examples of activity places	Level of development
Paragliding	Soft	Mount Spil, Kırtık Hill, Veziroğlu Hill, Karlık Hill, Bülbül Hill, Saruhanlı; Çınarlı Hill, Büyükbelen, Gördes; Şahinkaya	Middle
Hiking	Soft	Köseler-Aigai, Uncubozkoy-Sultan Higland, Saruhanlı; Şatırlar-Kardere, Salihli; Adala-Hermos Canyon, Demirci; Akıncılar Road, Kula; Sandal Volcano-Gökçeören	Middle
Mountain biking	Soft-Hard	Uncubozköy-Turgutalp, Manisa-Çal Mountain, Kale Village-Muradiye	Weak
Horse riding	Soft	Osmaniye Footpath, Erenköy and its surroundings, Baklacı-Toygarlı, Akkeçili-Erenköy	Weak
Orienteering	Soft	Manisa center, Soma, Salihli, Akhisar, Demirci, Gördes	Weak
ATV safari	Soft	Mount Spil, Uncubozkoy, Obasya, Mesir Nature Park	Weak
Backpacking trips	Soft	Mount Spil, Mount Yunt, Bozdağlar Plateau	Weak
A visit to the geopark and fairy chimneys	Soft	Kula-Salihli Geopark, Kuladokya	Weak
Visiting the national park	Soft	Spil Mountain National Park	Well

Caving	Soft - Hard	Nurkadin, Pashaini, Yarık, Gördes; Oğulduruk	Weak
Forest recreational area	Soft	Sultan Higland, Süeyya, Mevlevihane, Akpınar, Çınarlı Çeşme, Akhisar; Çağlak, Demirci; Güdürdek, Kırkağaç; Çamlı, Turgutlu; Ovacık	Weel
Hunting	Soft	State Hunting Grounds: Osmançali, Kavakalan, Zeytinliova, Gökseki, Şahinkaya, Güneşli, Adala, Göktepe, Uluderbent Başalan, Kırkağaç, Sarıgöl	Weak
Archaeological discoveries	Soft	Aigai, Sardis, the tombs of the Lydian kings etc.	Middle
Educational programs	Soft	TÜBİTAK Education Programs	Middle
Local research trips	Soft	Mount Spil, Yunt Mountain, Bozdağlar Plateau, Kula-Salihli Geopark,, Kula houses and traditional bazaar, Adala canyon, Gökeyüp village	Middle
Local festivals	Soft	Akhisar Çağlak Festival, Akhisar Olive Harvest Festival, Manisa Mesir Festival, Traditional Yeşilyurt Grape Festival, Traditional Sarıgöl Sultani Grape Festival etc.	Weel
Volunteer tourism	Soft	TaTuTa Farms: Suri vineyard house, and A. C. Şener Farm	Middle

Source: Atlı (2019); Buğday Ekolojik Yaşamı Destekleme Derneği; Koday, Koday and Kızıllıkan (2018); Manisa İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü; Nazik and Bayarı, 2018; Şehzadeler Kaymakamlığı (2017); T.C. Manisa Valiliği (2013); T.C. Zafer Kalkınma Ajansı (2016a, 2016b); TKDK (2015); TMMOB Jeoloji Mühendisleri Odası; Türkiye Oryantiring Federasyonu; Yaman (2015); Yasak and Durukan (2017)

When we look at the current situation of tourists or travelers in Manisa, it is seen that they are composed of those who participate in hiking tours organized by mountain-nature clubs, those who participate in near-environment tours of travel agencies, amateur and professional athletes, students, academics and researchers. Young and middle-aged men come to the fore in the demographic characteristics of individual participants. In organized tours, the number of men and women is the same. In recent years, visits by women's groups and their participation in nature walks have also become quite common. Yet, it is hardly possible to mention the effects of adventure tourism in Manisa. Activities such as nature trainings, orienteering, ATV tours, hiking and trekking, mountain biking, exploration and research trips have set the stage for adventure tourism customers in Manisa to be made up of different cultures. Announcements about adventure tourism and the experiences of the participants are frequently shared on social media. On the other hand, the most important sector that can threaten adventure tourism in Manisa is the regional industry, and there is a risk of increasing environmental pollution (especially air and water pollution) if it grows uncontrollably (T.C. Zafer Kalkınma Ajansı, 2016b: 52).

4.3. Adventure tourism potential of natural resources

Mountains, higlands and plains: Manisa is a mountainous geography with elevations over 1000 meter: Bozdağlar Plateau (2070 m), Mount Demirci (1800 m),

Mount Spil (1513 m), Mount Yunt (1074 m), Mount Çomaklı-Dibek (1034 m) et al. Apart from these high mountains, the plains in Manisa are 100-meter-height around: Gediz, Alaşehir, Salihli, Turgutlu et al. (Manisa İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü). There are canyon valleys, caves, karst formations, peaks, waterfalls, Sülüklü Lake and Akpınar reed beds on the Spil rising from the edge of Manisa city center. Another interesting aspect of the Spil is its mythological significance. There are many recreation areas in the Spil. Among them, the Atalanı Higland provides service with picnic and camping area, chalets, country café and restaurant. The Sultan Higland is one of the most attractive recreation areas with its cherry orchards, pine trees, cold waters and cool air. While climbing the Mount Spil, the 900-meter-high viewing terrace is another recreational area (Semenderoğlu et al., 2005: 118-120; Yasak & Durukan, 2017: 328-330, 339). The Mount Spil was declared a National Park in 1968. 78 endemic plant species and wildlife are under protection in the National Park (Şehzadeler Kaymakamlığı, 2017: 5-6; Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Spil Mountain National Park

Source: <https://manisa.ktb.gov.tr>

Kula-Salihli volcanic area: Volcanic elements consist of Quaternary young alkali basaltic lava flows and tephra. Volcano cones, craters and lava flows are seen in this area, which has the youngest volcanism in Turkey (Körbalta, 2018: 201). This area was announced as “Kula-Salihli Geopark” in 2013 and was included in both the European Geoparks Network and the UNESCO Global Geoparks Network. The total area of the Geopark is 2320 km². The geopark has evidence of older than 200 million years of the earth’s past, and in this respect, it hosts a rich geodiversity. There is a special area called Kula-Fairy Chimneys/Kuladokya within the boundaries of the geopark (Fig. 4, 5, 6, 7).

Fig. 4. Kula-Salihli Geopark
Source: <http://www.manisa.gov.tr>

Fig. 5. Kula-Salihli Geopark
Source: <http://www.kulasalihligeopark.com>

Fig. 6. Adala Canyon (Kula-Salihli Geopark)
Source: <http://www.kulasalihligeopark.com>

Fig. 7. Kuladokya
Source: <http://www.manisa.gov.tr>

It was formed as a result of the erosion of volcanic materials by the branches of the Gediz River. Three new geosites, shaped by paleo-environmental conditions, global climate change, past volcanic processes, natural disasters, and of great importance in terms of geo-heritage and earth sciences, have been identified in the geopark area (Aytaç & Demir, 2019: 125-140; Kula-Salihli Geopark; Ege, 2019).

Vegetation and wildlife: Depending on the altitude, lowland plants, maquis, drought-resistant and evergreen Mediterranean flora and forests are distributed. Forests are generally found in communities at altitudes above 150 meters. Acorn, oak, red pine, larch, hornbeam, poplar etc. are common forest plants. 593 plant species have been identified in the Mount Spil and 78 of them are endemic. The Manisa tulip, as an endemic species, is important for ecotourism and botanical tourism. Among the natural medicinal plants, mainly marshmallow, vinaigrette, mallow, licorice, poppy, foxglove, mullein, chicory, nettle etc. grows. The basic elements of wildlife in the Spil are roe deer, hawk, vulture, wild pigeon, partridge, stork, duck, wild goose, etc. Abandoned and wild horses roam in herds in the Atalanı locality (Semenderoğlu et al., 2005: 119; TKDK, 2015: 38-39).

Water resources: The Gediz River, Bakırçay River, Gölmarmara Lake and geothermal waters are the main water resources of Manisa. Sülüklügöl, a small lake at an altitude of 600 meters in the National Park, was formed by the melting of limestones (Yasak & Durukan, 2017: 329). The Gölmarmara has an area of 3400 ha and its depth is 3-4 meters. The lake, which is surrounded by reeds, has a rich natural

environment with bird diversity. Geothermal waters are distributed in many districts of the province and some of them serve in thermal tourism (Salihli-Kurşunlu et al.), and the waters are bottled and sold as mineral water (Manisa İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü; TKDK, 2015: 41).

Climate: Manisa is within the boundaries of the Mediterranean macro-climate region and topographic features create local climatic conditions. The annual average temperature is 17.5°C and the annual precipitation average is 714 mm. In the center of Manisa, an average of 162 summer days per year has been determined. The annual average number of days when the temperature drops below zero is 26. The precipitation is generally seen in the winter, while the summers are dry. It rains on average 82 days a year (Manisa İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü; Yasak & Durukan, 2017: 321, TKDK, 2015: 35).

4.4. Reassessment of adventure tourism potential and SWOT analysis

The current situation of adventure tourism in Manisa and the natural resources suitable for this type of tourism are presented in the Subsections 4.1, 4.2 and Table 4. Since the adventure tourism in Manisa cannot perform fully with these resources and activities, the question of what other innovations can be made comes to mind. In addition, there should also be answers to the following questions:

- 1) What types of tourism are currently practiced in the countryside of Manisa?
- 2) What is the state of the transport and communication infrastructure in the difficult geographies that can be called as isolated in the countryside of Manisa?
- 3) Are there any political and legal obstacles or incentives that restrict the development of adventure tourism in the countryside of Manisa?
- 4) Where are the places where adventure tourism cannot/ should not be done in the countryside of Manisa?
- 5) Which types of tourism and their activities can be integrated with the adventure tourism in Manisa?
- 6) What are the local and regional risks that threaten the adventure tourism in Manisa?

Undoubtedly, answers to all these questions exceed the limits of this study. In this case, to transfer the strategies in the existing plans here is the most practical way. Manisa is a province of the TR33 Region. In the Current Situation Analysis of the TR33 Region of the Zafer Development Agency, the following sentence is important regarding Manisa's tourism: "Nature tourism, which includes sightseeing, hiking, research, observation and climbing activities, has an important potential in the TR33 Region" (T.C. Zafer Kalkınma Ajansı, 2016a: 48-54). In the 2014-2023 Regional Plan of the Agency, "the development of nature tourism, tourism activities will be diversified and increased" has found a place. Nature tourism is fully compatible with adventure tourism within the framework of strategic importance and projects in the plan. In addition, four places have been placed on the map as development centers of nature tourism: Menteşe (Soma), Mount Spil, Gölarmara Lake and the volcanic park (T.C. Zafer Kalkınma Ajansı, 2016b: 90-91). Another plan prepared in recent

years is the Manisa Tourism Brand City Strategic Development Plan. The name “adventure” is mentioned on many pages (nature tourism, bicycle tourism, youth tourism) in the Plan. The activities, brand values and strategies (orienteering tourism, jeep safari tourism, motocross and ATV tourism, hunting and fishing tourism, paragliding) under the title of “adrenalin tourism” belong entirely to adventure tourism. In addition, rural tourism, ecotourism, highland tourism, bird watching tourism, equestrian tourism, photo safari tourism, etc., which are widely covered in the plan, intersect with adventure tourism (T.C. Manisa Valiliği, 2013: 461). Although the name of “adventure tourism” is not mentioned in a project prepared for the development of rural tourism in Manisa (TKDK, 2015), ecotourism, nature tourism, highland and mountain tourism, which is claimed to have potential, is directly related to adventure tourism. The most focused plan on the adventure tourism in Manisa is the Mountain Spil Tourism and Investment Action Plan. In two parts of the plan, issues that directly concern adventure tourism are included. Opinions on the diversification of nature-adventure products are quite extensive (Şehzadeler Belediyesi, 2017: 69-74).

The authors of this study present the following recommendations in the table below (Table 5, Fig. 8)

Table 5. New activities, places of application and things to do that can be developed in adventure tourism in Manisa

New activities	Type	Examples of new activity areas (potential)	Needs to be done
Flora and fauna study trips, photo safari, mini train, battery powered vehicles, etc. with the discovery tour.	Soft	Spil Mountain National Park, Mount Yunt, Bozdağlar Plateau, Gediz River, Gölarmara Lake, Kula-Salihli Geopark, Kuladokya, Alaşehir, Salihli, Turgutlu, vineyards, olive groves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Adventure tourism should take its place as a strategy in public and local government plans. ▪ Young people and staff of a total of 12 universities located in Manisa and the surrounding provinces are a potential customer base. Special package tours, promotional and marketing activities should be carried out for this large group.
Canoeing, etc. water activities.	Soft - Hard	Gediz River, Adala Canyon, Demirköprü, Sevişler and Afşar dams.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Instead of implementing a large number of activities in many places within the scope of adventure tourism in Manisa, those with brand value should be selected and focused on certain places. ▪ In order to prevent the harmful consequences of adventure tourism that will be concentrated in certain
Entertainment-sports-exploration-children’s parks for educational purposes, thematic parks, summer camps and summer schools.	Soft	Spil Mountain National Park, Mount Yunt, Bozdağlar Plateau, Kula-Salihli Geopark	
Cooking workshops in natural environments (mountain, forest).	Soft	Spil Mountain National Park, Mount Yunt, Bozdağlar Plateau, Kula-Salihli Geopark, forest recreational areas	
Handicraft	Soft	Manisa; Örselli, Salihli;	

workshops in the villages.		Gökeyüp	<p>areas in Manisa, the carrying capacity of this place should be determined.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D projects related to adventure tourism should be encouraged in Manisa, funds and sponsors should be found for investment projects. Scientific publications related to adventure tourism in Manisa should be multiplied.
Youth tourism and camping-caravan tourism	Soft	Spil Mountain National Park, Mount Yunt, Bozdağlar Plateau, forest recreational areas	
Thermal tourism	Soft	Soma; Menteşe, Salihli; Sart, Kurşunlu, Turgutlu; Urganlı, Saraycık, Kula; Emir	
Agricultural tourism and gastronomy tourism	Soft	Alaşehir, Kula, Salihli, Kırkağaç, Akhisar	
Coal mine visits	Soft - Hard	Soma	

Source: TKDK (2015); Yasak and Durukan (2017); <https://manisa.ktb.gov.tr>

Fig. 8. Activity areas of adventure tourism and potential new areas in Manisa

Base Map: <https://www.google.com.tr/maps/@38.7564395,28.2292029,9z/data=!5m1!1e4>

When a SWOT analysis is made on the basis of important natural attractions, current and suggested activities, places of application and other factors for adventure tourism in Manisa, the most important result is that the strengths and opportunities of adventure tourism in Manisa are far ahead of the weaknesses and threats (Table 6).

Table 6. SWOT analysis of adventure tourism in Manisa

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The opportunity to do adventure tourism in four seasons; ▪ Different images of nature and their rich charm: mountains, volcanic terrain, interesting natural formations, plains, highlands, forests, endemic plant species and unique natural landscapes; ▪ Rural cultural originality: carpet-rug weaving, authentic ceramic products, local cuisine, preserved villages, rural cultural landscapes typical of the Aegean Region, etc.; ▪ Rich agricultural culture and brand products: grapes, olives, olive oil, melons, watermelons, cherries, sesame seeds, vegetables, etc.; ▪ Mount Spil National Park; ▪ Kula-Salihli Geopark and Kuladokya; ▪ Geothermal waters and accommodation facilities; ▪ Adequacy of the road transport network in the countryside; ▪ The presence of an international airport in the immediate vicinity (64 km, 60 min); ▪ Safe zone; ▪ Hospitable rural people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intensification of adventure tourism in spring and autumn; ▪ Lack of full knowledge of the potential of adventure tourism; ▪ Natural resources have not been converted into tourist products for adventure purposes; ▪ Lack of adventure-oriented services; ▪ Lack of evaluation of marketing opportunities; ▪ Lack of specialization and professional education about nature-based types of tourism; ▪ Poor tourism entrepreneurship in the countryside and management difficulties.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Socio-demographic trends and changes; ▪ Further spread of the soft genre in adventure tourism; ▪ The correspondence of individualization in tourism with adventure tourism; ▪ Growing market at regional, national and global scale, development of marketing partnerships; ▪ More preference for niche products; ▪ Increase in package tours that combine active holidays, health, sports and experience in natural environments; ▪ The role of adventure tourism in rural socio-economic development; ▪ The support of new trends such as digital tourism, creative tourism, and the sharing economy in tourism to adventure tourism; ▪ The making of regional and national plans, funds and projects related to tourism and development; ▪ The presence of a high number of university youth in the region, the creation of a group of travelers and backpackers, sports, adventure, educational and exploration-oriented travelers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental problems, natural disaster risks; ▪ Economic investments and activities incompatible with nature; ▪ Negative consequences of global climate change on regional weather conditions; ▪ Lack of health safety, equipment, expert guidance and legislation; ▪ The large number of tourist attractions and types of tourism at the national and regional levels leads to competition; ▪ There are very few tour operators and travel agencies specializing in adventure tourism; ▪ Lack of demand caused by lack of publicity and awareness.

5. Conclusion

With this research, it was aimed to determine the suitability of natural resources in Manisa Province for adventure tourism. Accordingly, a literature review and land observations were conducted. The geographical location of Manisa, its geomorphological and climatological conditions, hospitable local people are the first signs that adventure tourism can develop in this province. Apart from these, there are also obstacles, inadequacies and risks in front of adventure tourism in the province (Subsection 4.4., Tables 5, 6). All these findings indicate that the study has achieved its goal. The comment that all of the hypotheses have been confirmed can be made about the four hypotheses identified at the beginning of the study. Only some additions can be made to hypothesis (3) (there are many obstacles to adventure tourism in Manisa): many sub-headings can be included in the scope of "barriers", such as lack of vision, apathy and unconsciousness, legal-administrative problems. In this case, it would not be wrong to say that all obstacles to adventure tourism in Manisa are "human".

The results of the study are detailed in Section 4. In order not to go into repetition here, high-level generalizations would be made. Considering the SWOT analysis, the attractiveness factors in its background (Subsection 4.4) and the global trends in adventure tourism (Sub-subsection 4.1.5), the following holistic comments can be made about the future of adventure tourism in Manisa: first, the available activities and places of practice are quite limited. The reason for this limitedness is not the weakness of natural attractions, but the lack of vision, policy, strategy and initiatives on the development of adventure tourism. Secondly, the new activities that can be applied to adventure tourism in Manisa must be compatible with the innovations in the world. For example, national parks, geoparks and mountains are the most suitable geographical environments for children's education and amusement parks, thematic parks, summer camps and summer schools, food and craft workshops, backpacker, solo traveler and women-only services, and all other activities. Third, the adventure tourism in Manisa should be integrated with many types of tourism (ecotourism, rural tourism, nature tourism, thermal tourism) that have reached a certain level of development. Opportunity should be given to add the undeveloped types (agrotourism, bicycle tourism, camping-caravan tourism, etc.) to adventure tourism. Fourth, it is difficult to pinpoint the positive and negative effects of the adventure tourism in Manisa up until now. Neither there is sufficient development, nor a long time has passed, nor there is any data. However, it should be known that an adventure tourism developed with plans and programs can be a driving force for rural development, especially in the mountainous areas of the province. Having two protected areas in Manisa means the controlled development of adventure tourism, here and environmental problems will not be so negative. Fifth, global trends in adventure tourism should be adapted to Manisa. These are not just diversification of activities. The main thing is that the current trends in tourism (concepts; sustainable, slow, green, governance, and approaches; responsible, protectionist, participatory, social and technological innovative, etc.) are moving to

Manisa. The most important thing is to bring the current trends in tourism (concepts; sustainable, slow, green, governance, approaches; responsible, protective, participatory, social and technological innovation etc.) to Manisa. In this direction, public and private sector partnerships should be ensured, and all tourism stakeholders should be invited to plans, programs and projects. In particular, the local people should not be neglected and their opinions, suggestions and requests should definitely be taken into account (Özşahin, 2015: 767-768; Türk & Güneren, 2021: 351-375).

The study is a very important reference source for Manisa and the Aegean Region. Among the reasons for this importance are to draw attention to adventure tourism and to raise awareness because adventure tourism can serve the policy of expanding tourism and diversifying tourism in Manisa and the region. Another important aspect of the study is that it contributes to the tourism sector, tourism academy and tourism geography literature in terms of approach, methods and findings. Finally, the issue that needs to be emphasized is that further research should be conducted on the adventure tourism in Manisa. The following topics can be suggested: new developments in soft and hard adventure genres and identification of application areas; development of perception, image and awareness in adventure tourism; encouraging regional university youth to adventure tourism; local community-adventure tourism relationship; legislation, entrepreneurship and management in adventure tourism; leveraging social media and digital technology, and so on.

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